
Plan Overview

A Data Management Plan created using DMPonline

Title: Effects of Advanced Trauma Life Support® Training Compared to Standard Care on Adult Trauma Patient Outcomes: A Cluster Randomised Trial

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Funder: Swedish Research Council

Template: Swedish Research Council Template

Project abstract:

Trauma is a massive global health issue. Many training programmes have been developed to help physicians in the initial management of trauma patients. Advanced Trauma Life Support® (ATLS®) is the most popular of these programmes and have been used to train over one million physicians worldwide. Despite its widespread use, there are no controlled trials showing that ATLS® improves patient outcomes. Multiple systematic reviews stress the need for such trials.

We will conduct a batched stepped wedge cluster randomised controlled trial with the aim to compare the effects of ATLS® training with standard care on outcomes in adult trauma patients. Cluster will be hospitals in India. We will roll out the intervention of ATLS® training to 32 clusters organised in four batches. Within each batch, clusters will be randomised to one of eight implementation sequences. We expect a sample size of 6528 patients over five years.

This is a collaborative project between researchers and institutions in Sweden, India, and the United Kingdom. Our research will be important regardless of whether the results are positive or negative. If we show that ATLS® improves patient outcomes then ATLS® should be promoted to save lives and reduce morbidity. If we show that ATLS does not improve patient outcomes then this should impact how trauma life support training is delivered and new course concepts may be needed.

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Effects of Advanced Trauma Life Support® Training Compared to Standard Care on Adult Trauma Patient Outcomes: A Cluster Randomised Trial

General Information

Effects of Advanced Trauma Life Support® Training Compared to Standard Care on Mortality and Functional Outcomes in Adult Trauma Patients

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N/A

1.3

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Description of data - reuse of existing data and/or production of new data

The protocol and data definitions, including metadata, will be pre-defined and uploaded to clinicaltrials.gov according to the Protocol Registration Data Element Definitions.

The project codebook will comprehensively document metadata such as encompassing variable definitions, data collection procedures, and valid value ranges. Data collection will be conducted by clinical research coordinators, specifically employed for this task. They will gather data as defined in the codebook. Coordinators will employ paper-based case record forms (CRFs) for initial data collection where each participant will be assigned a unique patient ID. CRFs will be stored in accordance with local regulations at each site. An electronic data collection tool will be used to upload the data, with each site having its own unique URL. The data collection tool is accessible exclusively via VPN with two-factor authentication. Data backups will occur at least every 24 hours. Long-term data storage will take place on KI servers in Sweden. All data transfers between servers will be conducted through encrypted VPN solutions.

The codebook will be made available in a data sharing repository (e.g., GitHub or Zenodo), connected to a unique DOI. Upon the publication of the primary research findings, an anonymised version of the dataset will be released under the same DOI as the metadata. The data will be shared under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 license.

A pilot study for this study estimates that approximately 75 variables per patient will be collected. Sample size calculations indicate a total of 6500-7000 patients to be included. The accumulated data is anticipated to remain below 500 MB in size, consisting exclusively of tabular text data. Data storage and will be facilitated through a secure database with API access, as well as archival and processing of .csv files on secure servers.

Documentation and data quality

No specific metadata vocabulary will be used. However, we will use standard vocabulary and keywords that are commonly used in clinical and injury research as much as possible. This includes for example the collection of injuries that will be categorised using ICD-10. Metadata with details on variable collection and valid value ranges will be included in the project codebook.

Given environmental constraints, the initial data collection will be conducted on paper. Each participant will be assigned a unique ID upon inclusion. Pseudonymised data will be uploaded using an online data collection tool which incorporates the codebook and implements data validation to ensure reliable input. Moreover, critical variables will be entered twice to minimise the risk of errors. The data collection tool is accessible only over VPN with two-factor authentication.

Storage and backup

The metadata, in form of the codebook, will be openly accessible from the start of data collection. It will be hosted in an online repository to allow version handling and have a persistent DOI. The collected data is backed up at least daily and also transferred over secure VPNs to secondary project servers daily.

Clinical research coordinators will use paper-based case record forms (CRFs) to collect data, assigning a unique patient ID to each participant. CRFs will be stored securely on-site in accordance with local regulations. Uploaded data will be pseudonymised, and patient IDs will only be linked to patient names and details through the CRF.

Access to the digital data requires secure VPN connections with two-factor authentication, which can only be granted by the project PI or a delegated person. To ensure the data never leaves project servers, data analysis will be conducted by granting remote work access to the pseudonymised dataset.

Legal and ethical aspects

The project PI bears overall responsibility for the integrity and security of the data. Handling of personal data occurs exclusively at each site by the local PI and clinical research coordinators. Throughout the collection process, access to digital pseudonymised data for all sites will be restricted to the project PI, data manager, and authorised personnel delegated by the project PI. Site PIs and clinical research officers will have access to data only for their respective sites.

Personal data will be handled in accordance with GDPR regulations and the requirements of the relevant ethical permits. We will seek ethical clearance for the study from local Institutional Review Board (IRB) committees at each study site, as well as from the Swedish Ethical Review Authority. Given the reduced decisional capacity of the intended patient cohort and the nature of the intervention, obtaining patient informed consent is neither feasible nor appropriate. We will seek a waiver of informed consent from the review boards. However, we will seek consent for follow-up after discharge.

Accessibility and long-term storage

The metadata, including version history, will be readily available as outlined and accessible from the start of data collection. To safeguard participant integrity, individual patient-level data will remain inaccessible until the project's completion. Upon the conclusion of the project and concurrent with the main project publication, an anonymised version of the dataset will be released under the same persistent DOI as the published metadata. Hence, our data and metadata will be accessible since a persistent identifier assigned by the repository will lead to them.

All data will be released under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 license.

The metadata and anonymised dataset will be made openly available for reuse. In compliance with Swedish law, all research data will be archived at KI for a minimum duration of 10 years following the project's completion. The selection of long-term storage data will be decided by the project PI in collaboration with the delegated data manager(s). The site CRFs will be archived according to local regulations. We plan to make our data reusable by assuring high data quality and providing detailed documentation and metadata to support correct interpretation. Licensing will be clearly outlined in the repository when accessing the data.

Data and metadata will be released in common formats, plain text CSV and HTML to allow for interoperability. The anonymised data will also be released as a software package in R. Metadata will be available in both package descriptions and in CSV format.

We will create a persistent DOI by using Zenodo for the metadata, hosted in a GitHub repository. This will allow for versioning of the metadata. Once completed, the anonymised dataset will be released to the same repository and accessible by the same DOI.

Responsibility and resources

The project PI has overall responsibility for research data, including archiving. Local PIs are responsible for data handling at their respective sites. The project data manager, appointed by the project PI, will assist local PIs and other collaborators in data handling throughout the project.

The technical infrastructure and human resources required for the solutions described in this plan are already in place. All data will be stored on project servers with backups and long-term storage access provisions. The project data manager and PI will continuously review the plan to ensure compliance with the FAIR principles.